

Extended data

Supplementary material for the article 'Association between living with children, vaccination, and outcomes from COVID-19: an OpenSAFELY cohort study of 12 million adults in England during 2021-22' in Wellcome Open Research.

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Figure S1: Adjusted* hazard ratios (HRs) for SARS-CoV-2 infection, COVID-19 hospital admission, and COVID-19 death, among adults aged >65 years, between 20th December 2020 and 21st February 2022 (versus adults with no children in the household)

*Adjusted for age, sex, ethnicity, number of adults in household, IMD, BMI, smoking, hypertension or high blood pressure, chronic respiratory disease, asthma, cancer, chronic liver disease, stroke or dementia, other neurological disease, reduced kidney function, end-stage renal disease, solid organ transplant, asplenia, rheumatoid, lupus or psoriasis, other immunosuppressive condition.

Figure S2: Adjusted* hazard ratios (HRs) for SARS-CoV-2 infection, COVID-19 hospital admission, and COVID-19 death (versus no children in the household and being unvaccinated) in adults aged >65 years (20th December 2020 to 21st February 2022), by number of vaccine doses

No doses

(a) SARS-CoV-2 infection

(b) COVID-19 hospital admission

(c) COVID-19 death

*For age, sex, ethnicity, number adults in household, IMD, BMI, smoking, hypertension/high blood pressure, chronic respiratory disease, asthma, cancer, chronic liver disease, stroke or dementia, other neurological disease, reduced kidney function, end-stage renal disease, solid organ transplant, asplenia, rheumatoid, lupus or psoriasis, other immunosuppressive condition

Figure S3: Adjusted hazard ratios (HRs) and 95% confidence intervals among adults aged ≤ 65 years before (left column) or after (right column) all children aged 12-17 in the household were double-vaccinated (if occurred)

Number of vaccine doses received by adults:

No doses

(a) SARS-CoV-2 infection

Before child vaccination

After child vaccination

(b) COVID-19 hospital admission

Before child vaccination

After child vaccination

(c) COVID-19 death

Before child vaccination

After child vaccination

Figure S4: Adjusted hazard ratios (HRs) and 95% confidence intervals (CI) for having SARS-CoV-2 infection or a SARS-CoV-2 test, compared to having no children in the household, in adults aged ≤ 65 years old

Table S1: Cohort description, by presence of children in the household, among adults aged ≤65 years

	Total cohort		No children		Only children aged 0-11 years		Only children aged 12-17 years		Children aged 0-11 and 12-17 years	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Overall	9417278	100	5978347	100	1809116	100	928457	100	701358	100
Age group										
18-29	1883371	20.0	1299693	21.7	320562	17.7	176921	19.1	86195	12.3
30-39	2230436	23.7	1069428	17.9	832328	46.0	96348	10.4	232332	33.1
40-49	2056361	21.8	904048	15.1	490703	27.1	357750	38.5	303860	43.3
50-59	2143529	22.8	1680258	28.1	126399	7.0	269611	29.0	67261	9.6
60-65	1103581	11.7	1024920	17.1	39124	2.2	27827	3.0	11710	1.7
Sex										
Female	4805589	51.0	2869363	48.0	1035469	57.2	508706	54.8	392051	55.9
Male	4611689	49.0	3108984	52.0	773647	42.8	419751	45.2	309307	44.1
BMI (kg/m²)										
<18.5	175508	1.9	118272	2.0	32531	1.8	14050	1.5	10655	1.5
18.5-24.9	2803578	29.8	1788113	29.9	582418	32.2	245549	26.5	187498	26.7
25-29.9	2547504	27.1	1601166	26.8	504189	27.9	250382	27.0	191767	27.3
30-34.9 (Obese class I)	1318158	14.0	839783	14.1	242434	13.4	133639	14.4	102302	14.6
35-39.9 (Obese class II)	546595	5.8	350111	5.9	98244	5.4	55312	6.0	42928	6.1
≥40 (Obese class III)	305504	3.2	197087	3.3	53962	3.0	30498	3.3	23957	3.4
<i>Missing</i>	1720431	18.3	1083815	18.1	295338	16.3	199027	21.4	142251	20.3
Smoking										
Never	4494233	47.7	2854171	47.7	877392	48.5	444605	47.9	318065	45.4
Former	2736887	29.1	1716209	28.7	545300	30.1	271507	29.2	203871	29.1
Current	1893651	20.1	1237644	20.7	344039	19.0	160709	17.3	151259	21.6
<i>Missing</i>	292507	3.1	170323	2.9	42385	2.3	51636	5.6	28163	4.0
Ethnicity										
White	7838500	83.2	5131365	85.8	1440336	79.6	749792	80.8	517007	73.7

Mixed	159748	1.7	96095	1.6	33538	1.9	15546	1.7	14569	2.1
South Asian	818128	8.7	394972	6.6	213040	11.8	102821	11.1	107295	15.3
Black	307429	3.3	169916	2.8	62740	3.5	35740	3.9	39033	5.6
Other	293473	3.1	185999	3.1	59462	3.3	24558	2.7	23454	3.3
IMD fifth										
1 (least deprived)	1789467	19.0	1117822	18.7	354262	19.6	201650	21.7	115733	16.5
2	1881242	20.0	1231352	20.6	348347	19.3	185540	20.0	116003	16.5
3	1944944	20.7	1278516	21.4	357491	19.8	180973	19.5	127964	18.3
4	2034824	21.6	1299235	21.7	389078	21.5	187589	20.2	158922	22.7
5 (most deprived)	1766801	18.8	1051422	17.6	359938	19.9	172705	18.6	182736	26.1
Total number of adults in household										
1	2259065	24.0	1787629	29.9	286387	15.8	105333	11.3	79716	11.4
2	3832872	40.7	2079031	34.8	1019645	56.4	373968	40.3	360228	51.4
3+	3325341	35.3	2111687	35.3	503084	27.8	449156	48.4	261414	37.3
Blood pressure										
Normal	2449531	26.0	1373305	23.0	614867	34.0	244739	26.4	216620	30.9
Elevated	1352010	14.4	842031	14.1	277492	15.3	129656	14.0	102831	14.7
High Stage 1	2980865	31.7	1935788	32.4	530312	29.3	298739	32.2	216026	30.8
High Stage 2	1614424	17.1	1140891	19.1	217730	12.0	157380	17.0	98423	14.0
<i>Missing</i>	1020448	10.8	686332	11.5	168715	9.3	97943	10.6	67458	9.6
High blood pressure or diagnosed hypertension	2304695	24.5	1671858	28.0	282654	15.6	219119	23.6	131064	18.7
Any comorbidity*	2930356	31.1	1970251	33.0	481788	26.6	281530	30.3	196787	28.1

BMI: body mass index; IMD: Index of Multiple Deprivation. *Any comorbidity includes: chronic respiratory disease, asthma, chronic cardiac disease, diabetes, cancer, end-stage renal disease, chronic liver disease, stroke or dementia, other neurological disease, other transplant, asplenia, Rheumatoid/Lupus/ Psoriasis or other immunosuppressive condition.

Table S2: Cohort description, by presence of children in the household, among adults aged >65 years

	Total cohort		No children		Only children aged 0-11 years		Only children aged 12-17 years		Children aged 0-11 and 12-17 years	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Overall	2866602	100	2774814	100	44519	100	31107	100	16162	100
Age group										
66-69	664546	23.2	631387	22.8	17840	40.1	9606	30.9	5713	35.4
70-79	1461882	51.0	1416747	51.1	21282	47.8	15882	51.1	7971	49.3
80+	740174	25.8	726680	26.2	5397	12.1	5619	18.1	2478	15.3
Sex										
Female	1542190	53.8	1493443	53.8	23393	52.6	16227	52.2	9127	56.5
Male	1324412	46.2	1281371	46.2	21126	47.5	14880	47.8	7035	43.5
BMI (kg/m²)										
<18.5	55458	1.9	54077	2.0	622	1.4	514	1.7	245	1.5
18.5-24.9	859519	30.0	836209	30.1	11588	26.0	7743	24.9	3979	24.6
25-29.9	1038593	36.2	1006337	36.3	15745	35.4	11003	35.4	5508	34.1
30-34.9 (Obese class I)	506795	17.7	489113	17.6	8454	19.0	6019	19.4	3209	19.9
35-39.9 (Obese class II)	168888	5.9	162547	5.9	2939	6.6	2284	7.3	1118	6.9
≥40 (Obese class III)	66972	2.3	64291	2.3	1267	2.9	919	3.0	495	3.1
<i>Missing</i>	<i>170377</i>	<i>5.9</i>	<i>162240</i>	<i>5.9</i>	<i>3904</i>	<i>8.8</i>	<i>2625</i>	<i>8.4</i>	<i>1608</i>	<i>10.0</i>
Smoking										
Never	1140582	39.8	1096711	39.5	21562	48.4	13865	44.6	8444	52.3
Former	1485233	51.8	1447902	52.2	17803	40.0	13735	44.2	5793	35.8
Current	233436	8.1	223884	8.1	4622	10.4	3253	10.5	1677	10.4
<i>Missing</i>	<i>7351</i>	<i>0.3</i>	<i>6317</i>	<i>0.2</i>	<i>532</i>	<i>1.2</i>	<i>254</i>	<i>0.8</i>	<i>248</i>	<i>1.5</i>
Ethnicity										
White	2710876	94.6	2649034	95.5	29493	66.3	23121	74.3	9228	57.1
Mixed	10493	0.4	9359	0.3	551	1.2	368	1.2	215	1.3
South Asian	92990	3.2	71014	2.6	11166	25.1	5541	17.8	5269	32.6

Black	28772	1.0	24957	0.9	1744	3.9	1254	4.0	817	5.1
Other	23471	0.8	20450	0.7	1565	3.5	823	2.7	633	3.9
IMD fifth										
1 (least deprived)	713496	24.9	696735	25.1	8010	18.0	6157	19.8	2594	16.1
2	681426	23.8	663714	23.9	8587	19.3	6249	20.1	2876	17.8
3	615900	21.5	596542	21.5	9560	21.5	6588	21.2	3210	19.9
4	506794	17.7	486368	17.5	10050	22.6	6566	21.1	3810	23.6
5 (most deprived)	348986	12.2	331455	12.0	8312	18.7	5547	17.8	3672	22.7
Total number of adults in household										
1	976323	34.1	972901	35.1	1455	3.3	1690	5.4	277	1.7
2	1476644	51.5	1459112	52.6	7682	17.3	7701	24.8	2149	13.3
3+	413635	14.4	342801	12.4	35382	79.5	21716	69.8	13736	85.0
Blood pressure										
Normal	315778	11.0	305348	11.0	5048	11.3	3528	11.3	1854	11.5
Elevated	439336	15.3	425760	15.3	6588	14.8	4593	14.8	2395	14.8
High Stage 1	1064323	37.1	1030631	37.1	16470	37.0	11385	36.6	5837	36.1
High Stage 2	1032042	36.0	1000379	36.1	15109	33.9	11024	35.4	5530	34.2
<i>Missing</i>	<i>15123</i>	<i>0.5</i>	<i>12696</i>	<i>0.5</i>	<i>1304</i>	<i>2.9</i>	<i>577</i>	<i>1.9</i>	<i>546</i>	<i>3.4</i>
High blood pressure or diagnosed hypertension	2003453	69.9	1941381	70.0	29744	66.8	21455	69.0	10873	67.3
Any comorbidity*	1769618	61.7	1713541	61.8	26747	60.1	19381	62.3	9949	61.6

BMI: body mass index; IMD: Index of Multiple Deprivation. *Any comorbidity includes: chronic respiratory disease, asthma, chronic cardiac disease, diabetes, cancer, end-stage renal disease, chronic liver disease, stroke or dementia, other neurological disease, other transplant, asplenia, Rheumatoid/Lupus/ Psoriasis or other immunosuppressive condition.

Table S3: Hazard ratios (HRs) for SARS-CoV-2 infection, COVID-19 hospital admission, and COVID-19 death, stratified by time period and age group

(a) SARS-CoV-2 infection

Children in the household	Adults aged ≤65 years						Adults aged >65 years					
	No. of events	Person years	Rate (per 100,000 person years)	Age-sex adjusted	HR (95% CI) +Demographic adjusted*	+Comorbidity adjusted**	No. of events	Person years	Rate (per 100,000 person years)	Age-sex adjusted	HR (95% CI) +Demographic adjusted*	+Comorbidity adjusted**
Period 1												
None	188362	1357159	13879.14	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	44732	635374	7040.27	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	1 (ref)
Only children 0-11 years	73370	408927	17942.07	1.20 (1.19-1.21)	1.17 (1.15-1.18)	1.17 (1.16-1.18)	1342	10054	13347.27	1.77 (1.67-1.88)	1.25 (1.17-1.33)	1.24 (1.17-1.32)
Only children aged ≥12 years	37101	209960	17670.51	1.20 (1.18-1.21)	1.14 (1.12-1.16)	1.14 (1.13-1.16)	817	7036	11612.03	1.58 (1.46-1.70)	1.18 (1.09-1.27)	1.17 (1.08-1.26)
Children aged 0-11 and ≥12 years	29762	158346	18795.53	1.26 (1.24-1.28)	1.18 (1.17-1.20)	1.19 (1.17-1.20)	507	3633	13956.81	1.86 (1.69-2.04)	1.21 (1.10-1.33)	1.20 (1.09-1.32)
Period 2												
None	19425	2409476	806.19	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	2782	1135656	244.97	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	1 (ref)
Only children 0-11 years	9343	725419	1287.94	1.29 (1.25-1.33)	1.26 (1.22-1.29)	1.25 (1.22-1.29)	107	17678	605.26	2.54 (2.06-3.13)	1.65 (1.32-2.06)	1.64 (1.32-2.05)
Only children aged ≥12 years	3938	373472	1054.43	1.21 (1.16-1.26)	1.17 (1.13-1.22)	1.17 (1.13-1.22)	56	12415	451.06	1.87 (1.42-2.47)	1.35 (1.02-1.79)	1.34 (1.01-1.78)
Children aged 0-11 and ≥12 years	4176	281100	1485.59	1.53 (1.47-1.59)	1.45 (1.39-1.51)	1.45 (1.39-1.50)	56	6354	881.33	3.63 (2.74-4.80)	2.08 (1.55-2.81)	2.07 (1.53-2.79)
Period 3												
None	90380	3345986	2701.15	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	7661	1581369	484.45	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	1 (ref)
Only children 0-11 years	32419	1007959	3216.3	1.00 (0.99-1.02)	1.02 (1.00-1.03)	1.01 (1.00-1.03)	226	24507	922.19	1.73 (1.49-1.99)	1.36 (1.17-1.59)	1.36 (1.17-1.59)
Only children aged ≥12 years	19918	519690	3832.67	1.27 (1.25-1.29)	1.28 (1.26-1.31)	1.28 (1.26-1.30)	158	17238	916.59	1.78 (1.51-2.09)	1.45 (1.23-1.72)	1.45 (1.22-1.72)
Children aged 0-11 and ≥12 years	14483	390567	3708.2	1.20 (1.18-1.22)	1.26 (1.24-1.29)	1.26 (1.24-1.29)	89	8786	1012.95	1.92 (1.54-2.38)	1.46 (1.17-1.83)	1.45 (1.16-1.82)
Period 4												
None	104838	3982433	2632.51	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	19376	1906844	1016.13	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	1 (ref)
Only children 0-11 years	42606	1198542	3554.82	1.22 (1.20-1.23)	1.21 (1.20-1.23)	1.22 (1.20-1.23)	450	29444	1528.3	1.39 (1.26-1.54)	1.16 (1.04-1.29)	1.15 (1.04-1.29)
Only children aged ≥12 years	24092	616333	3908.93	1.36 (1.34-1.38)	1.36 (1.34-1.38)	1.36 (1.34-1.38)	359	20722	1732.45	1.63 (1.46-1.83)	1.40 (1.24-1.57)	1.39 (1.24-1.56)

Children aged 0-11 and ≥12 years	19085	463323	4119.16	1.44 (1.42-1.47)	1.46 (1.43-1.49)	1.46 (1.43-1.49)	183	10540	1736.16	1.60 (1.36-1.87)	1.27 (1.08-1.50)	1.26 (1.08-1.49)
Period 5												
None	324155	5476356	5919.17	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	58132	2654297	2190.11	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	1 (ref)
Only children 0-11 years	168236	1631403	10312.35	1.52 (1.50-1.53)	1.48 (1.47-1.50)	1.48 (1.47-1.50)	1494	40743	3666.87	1.50 (1.42-1.58)	1.43 (1.35-1.52)	1.43 (1.35-1.52)
Only children aged ≥12 years	77284	837795	9224.69	1.39 (1.38-1.41)	1.40 (1.39-1.41)	1.40 (1.39-1.41)	1012	28626	3535.2	1.52 (1.42-1.63)	1.46 (1.36-1.56)	1.45 (1.35-1.55)
Children aged 0-11 and ≥12 years	71338	626658	11383.88	1.67 (1.66-1.69)	1.75 (1.73-1.76)	1.75 (1.73-1.76)	522	14536	3591.17	1.51 (1.38-1.66)	1.46 (1.32-1.60)	1.45 (1.32-1.60)
Period 6												
None	277988	5862680	4741.65	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	56665	2950736	1920.37	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	1 (ref)
Only children 0-11 years	144193	1672389	8621.98	1.51 (1.50-1.53)	1.50 (1.48-1.51)	1.50 (1.49-1.51)	1225	44572	2748.35	1.28 (1.20-1.36)	1.23 (1.16-1.31)	1.23 (1.16-1.31)
Only children aged ≥12 years	55506	871239	6370.93	1.23 (1.22-1.24)	1.23 (1.21-1.24)	1.23 (1.21-1.24)	727	31328	2320.62	1.13 (1.05-1.22)	1.09 (1.00-1.18)	1.08 (1.00-1.17)
Children aged 0-11 and ≥12 years	48870	638155	7658.02	1.37 (1.36-1.39)	1.40 (1.38-1.41)	1.40 (1.38-1.41)	388	15874	2444.28	1.15 (1.04-1.28)	1.12 (1.00-1.25)	1.12 (1.00-1.24)

*Demographic adjusted model: Adjusted for age, sex, ethnicity, number adults in household, IMD, BMI, smoking.

**Comorbidity-adjusted model: Adjusted for age, sex, ethnicity, number adults in household, IMD, BMI, smoking, hypertension or high blood pressure, chronic respiratory disease, asthma, cancer, chronic liver disease, stroke or dementia, other neurological disease, reduced kidney function, end-stage renal disease, solid organ transplant, asplenia, rheumatoid, lupus or psoriasis, other immunosuppressive condition.

b) COVID-19 hospital admission

Children in the household	Adults aged ≤65 years						Adults aged >65 years					
	No. of events	Person years	Rate (per 100,000 person years)	HR (95% CI)			No. of events	Person years	Rate (per 100,000 person years)	HR (95% CI)		
				Age-sex adjusted	+Demographic adjusted*	+Comorbidity adjusted**				Age-sex adjusted	+Demographic adjusted*	+Comorbidity adjusted**
Period 1												
None	7632	1496619	509.95	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	10476	692297	1513.22	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	1 (ref)
Only children 0-11 years	1775	453976	390.99	1.27 (1.20-1.35)	1.14 (1.08-1.21)	1.15 (1.09-1.22)	309	11030	2801.36	1.88 (1.67-2.12)	1.26 (1.11-1.44)	1.25 (1.10-1.42)
Only children aged ≥12 years	1316	233131	564.49	1.26 (1.19-1.34)	1.15 (1.08-1.22)	1.16 (1.09-1.24)	211	7703	2739.02	1.78 (1.55-2.04)	1.27 (1.10-1.46)	1.25 (1.08-1.45)
Children aged 0-11 and ≥12 years	899	176094	510.52	1.41 (1.31-1.52)	1.15 (1.07-1.24)	1.17 (1.09-1.26)	119	3985	2985.96	1.93 (1.60-2.33)	1.17 (0.97-1.42)	1.14 (0.94-1.39)
Period 2												
None	431	2594527	16.61	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	283	1200151	23.58	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	1 (ref)
Only children 0-11 years	248	789855	31.4	2.05 (1.71-2.44)	1.82 (1.52-2.17)	1.84 (1.54-2.19)	10	18915	52.87	2.36 (1.24-4.48)	0.86 (0.43-1.73)	0.85 (0.43-1.71)
Only children aged ≥12 years	101	406212	24.86	1.45 (1.15-1.83)	1.29 (1.03-1.63)	1.31 (1.04-1.65)	10	13231	75.58	3.27 (1.73-6.17)	1.45 (0.75-2.81)	1.43 (0.74-2.76)
Children aged 0-11 and ≥12 years	124	306751	40.42	2.33 (1.88-2.88)	1.80 (1.44-2.24)	1.82 (1.46-2.27)	14	6804	205.76	8.48 (4.90-14.68)	2.50 (1.35-4.63)	2.40 (1.30-4.46)
Period 3												
None	1445	3552795	40.67	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	992	1643639	60.35	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	1 (ref)
Only children 0-11 years	623	1084216	57.46	1.39 (1.25-1.54)	1.37 (1.23-1.52)	1.40 (1.26-1.56)	39	25831	150.98	2.64 (1.90-3.68)	1.64 (1.15-2.34)	1.61 (1.13-2.31)
Only children aged ≥12 years	304	558306	54.45	1.37 (1.20-1.56)	1.33 (1.17-1.52)	1.36 (1.19-1.55)	34	18085	188	3.16 (2.24-4.46)	2.10 (1.47-3.01)	2.07 (1.45-2.97)
Children aged 0-11 and ≥12 years	334	421460	79.25	1.87 (1.65-2.12)	1.68 (1.48-1.92)	1.73 (1.52-1.97)	14	9271	151.01	2.50 (1.42-4.40)	1.36 (0.76-2.43)	1.31 (0.73-2.34)
Period 4												
None	1939	4289994	45.2	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	2427	1985065	122.26	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	1 (ref)
Only children 0-11 years	754	1312570	57.44	1.52 (1.38-1.67)	1.49 (1.35-1.64)	1.52 (1.38-1.68)	70	31151	224.71	2.02 (1.58-2.57)	1.47 (1.13-1.92)	1.46 (1.12-1.90)
Only children aged ≥12 years	372	676695	54.97	1.32 (1.17-1.48)	1.29 (1.14-1.45)	1.31 (1.17-1.48)	66	21820	302.47	2.58 (2.01-3.31)	1.99 (1.53-2.59)	1.97 (1.51-2.56)
Children aged 0-11 and ≥12 years	328	510597	64.24	1.60 (1.41-1.81)	1.42 (1.25-1.62)	1.47 (1.29-1.67)	36	11173	322.2	2.75 (1.97-3.83)	1.81 (1.28-2.58)	1.76 (1.24-2.50)
Period 5												
None	4125	5971390	69.08	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	5235	2761052	189.6	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	1 (ref)

Only children 0-11 years	1484	1831376	81.03	1.53 (1.43-1.64)	1.53 (1.43-1.64)	1.58 (1.47-1.69)	130	43221	300.78	1.81 (1.52-2.15)	1.40 (1.16-1.68)	1.38 (1.15-1.67)
Only children aged ≥12 years	810	944368	85.77	1.35 (1.25-1.46)	1.35 (1.25-1.47)	1.40 (1.29-1.52)	102	30257	337.11	1.90 (1.56-2.32)	1.52 (1.23-1.87)	1.49 (1.21-1.84)
Children aged 0-11 and ≥12 years	739	713011	103.65	1.79 (1.65-1.95)	1.70 (1.56-1.85)	1.77 (1.63-1.93)	56	15452	362.42	2.09 (1.59-2.73)	1.51 (1.15-2.00)	1.48 (1.12-1.96)
Period 6												
None	1456	6682326	21.79	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	2270	3075959	73.8	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	1 (ref)
Only children 0-11 years	605	2054507	29.45	1.65 (1.48-1.84)	1.65 (1.48-1.83)	1.79 (1.60-1.99)	58	48098	120.59	1.95 (1.50-2.54)	1.51 (1.14-2.01)	1.52 (1.14-2.02)
Only children aged ≥12 years	243	1060187	22.92	1.11 (0.96-1.28)	1.13 (0.98-1.30)	1.21 (1.05-1.39)	42	33608	124.97	1.85 (1.36-2.52)	1.49 (1.09-2.05)	1.48 (1.08-2.03)
Children aged 0-11 and ≥12 years	227	800531	28.36	1.51 (1.30-1.75)	1.45 (1.25-1.69)	1.62 (1.39-1.88)	28	17131	163.44	2.49 (1.72-3.62)	1.80 (1.22-2.66)	1.79 (1.21-2.66)

*Demographic adjusted model: Adjusted for age, sex, ethnicity, number adults in household, IMD, BMI, smoking.

**Comorbidity-adjusted model: Adjusted for age, sex, ethnicity, number adults in household, IMD, BMI, smoking, hypertension or high blood pressure, chronic respiratory disease, asthma, cancer, chronic liver disease, stroke or dementia, other neurological disease, reduced kidney function, end-stage renal disease, solid organ transplant, asplenia, rheumatoid, lupus or psoriasis, other immunosuppressive condition.

c) COVID-19 death

Children in the household	Adults aged ≤65 years						Adults aged >65 years					
	No. of events	Person years	Rate (per 100,000 person years)	HR (95% CI)			No. of events	Person years	Rate (per 100,000 person years)	HR (95% CI)		
				Age-sex adjusted	+Demographic adjusted*	+Comorbidity adjusted**				Age-sex adjusted	+Demographic adjusted*	+Comorbidity adjusted**
Period 1												
None	1446	1497713	96.55	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	8159	693477	1176.54	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	1 (ref)
Only children 0-11 years	142	454242	31.26	0.91 (0.75-1.10)	0.80 (0.67-0.97)	0.81 (0.67-0.98)	144	11068	1301.05	1.43 (1.21-1.70)	1.12 (0.93-1.33)	1.10 (0.92-1.32)
Only children aged ≥12 years	124	233332	53.14	0.83 (0.68-1.00)	0.79 (0.65-0.96)	0.80 (0.66-0.97)	94	7729	1216.26	1.18 (0.96-1.45)	0.97 (0.79-1.20)	0.96 (0.78-1.18)
Children aged 0-11 and ≥12 years	62	176231	35.18	0.84 (0.64-1.10)	0.70 (0.53-0.91)	0.72 (0.55-0.94)	59	4000	1474.97	1.49 (1.15-1.95)	1.06 (0.81-1.39)	1.04 (0.79-1.36)
Period 2												
None	71	2597522	2.73	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	274	1202888	22.78	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	1 (ref)
Only children 0-11 years	16	790613	2.02	2.25 (1.16-4.36)	2.09 (1.08-4.05)	2.09 (1.08-4.06)	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	15.78	0.93 (0.29-2.94)	0.50 (0.15-1.60)	0.49 (0.15-1.59)
Only children aged ≥12 years	15	406768	3.69	2.21 (1.25-3.92)	2.24 (1.25-4.01)	2.28 (1.27-4.10)	13	13293	97.8	5.14 (2.93-8.99)	3.16 (1.71-5.82)	3.11 (1.69-5.74)
Children aged 0-11 and ≥12 years	6	307140	1.95	1.79 (0.75-4.25)	1.58 (0.64-3.89)	1.61 (0.65-3.94)	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	73.08	3.86 (1.57-9.45)	1.67 (0.62-4.48)	1.63 (0.61-4.40)
Period 3												
None	89	3557123	2.5	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	264	1647371	16.03	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	1 (ref)
Only children 0-11 years	17	1085393	1.57	1.05 (0.58-1.92)	0.99 (0.54-1.81)	1.01 (0.55-1.84)	6	25965	23.11	1.66 (0.73-3.78)	0.80 (0.35-1.82)	0.79 (0.35-1.81)
Only children aged ≥12 years	16	559126	2.86	1.24 (0.72-2.14)	1.18 (0.67-2.05)	1.20 (0.69-2.10)	7	18172	38.52	2.59 (1.23-5.48)	1.38 (0.65-2.93)	1.37 (0.64-2.90)
Children aged 0-11 and ≥12 years	6	422063	1.42	0.75 (0.31-1.83)	0.63 (0.26-1.55)	0.66 (0.27-1.62)	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	21.45	1.41 (0.35-5.70)	0.56 (0.14-2.26)	0.54 (0.13-2.19)
Period 4												
None	298	4296253	6.94	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	1018	1990130	51.15	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	1 (ref)
Only children 0-11 years	27	1314448	2.05	0.61 (0.40-0.95)	0.60 (0.39-0.92)	0.62 (0.40-0.95)	33	31342	105.29	2.62 (1.84-3.72)	1.75 (1.19-2.57)	1.72 (1.16-2.54)
Only children aged ≥12 years	29	677903	4.28	0.84 (0.57-1.25)	0.85 (0.57-1.26)	0.85 (0.57-1.26)	25	21944	113.93	2.56 (1.72-3.81)	1.82 (1.19-2.77)	1.79 (1.18-2.74)
Children aged 0-11 and ≥12 years	16	511569	3.13	0.78 (0.46-1.32)	0.68 (0.40-1.18)	0.72 (0.42-1.24)	18	11250	160	3.68 (2.30-5.89)	2.18 (1.32-3.62)	2.11 (1.27-3.53)
Period 5												
None	540	5982174	9.03	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	2072	2770172	74.8	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	1 (ref)

Only children 0-11 years	70	1834862	3.82	1.04 (0.79-1.37)	1.08 (0.82-1.42)	1.11 (0.84-1.46)	51	43538	117.14	2.07 (1.56-2.75)	1.64 (1.21-2.21)	1.63 (1.21-2.20)
Only children aged ≥12 years	74	946491	7.82	1.22 (0.94-1.58)	1.29 (1.00-1.68)	1.33 (1.02-1.72)	35	30481	114.83	1.79 (1.28-2.51)	1.46 (1.04-2.05)	1.43 (1.02-2.01)
Children aged 0-11 and ≥12 years	43	714763	6.02	1.32 (0.95-1.83)	1.29 (0.93-1.80)	1.34 (0.97-1.87)	15	15584	96.25	1.57 (0.92-2.70)	1.18 (0.68-2.04)	1.17 (0.67-2.02)
Period 6												
None	193	6698319	2.88	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	1396	3089877	45.18	1 (ref)	1 (ref)	1 (ref)
Only children 0-11 years	17	2059917	0.83	0.64 (0.38-1.10)	0.71 (0.42-1.21)	0.74 (0.43-1.26)	22	48550	45.31	1.51 (0.98-2.31)	1.42 (0.90-2.22)	1.42 (0.90-2.22)
Only children aged ≥12 years	16	1063359	1.5	0.72 (0.42-1.23)	0.82 (0.48-1.41)	0.85 (0.50-1.45)	16	33934	47.15	1.33 (0.81-2.17)	1.28 (0.77-2.12)	1.25 (0.76-2.07)
Children aged 0-11 and ≥12 years	17	803214	2.12	1.35 (0.78-2.32)	1.38 (0.80-2.38)	1.48 (0.86-2.54)	12	17327	69.26	2.05 (1.16-3.62)	1.88 (1.02-3.46)	1.87 (1.01-3.45)

*Demographic adjusted model: Adjusted for age, sex, ethnicity, number adults in household, IMD, BMI, smoking.

**Comorbidity-adjusted model: Adjusted for age, sex, ethnicity, number adults in household, IMD, BMI, smoking, hypertension or high blood pressure, chronic respiratory disease, asthma, cancer, chronic liver disease, stroke or dementia, other neurological disease, reduced kidney function, end-stage renal disease, solid organ transplant, asplenia, rheumatoid, lupus or psoriasis, other immunosuppressive condition.

Methods: Secondary analyses

Testing behaviour

We used the control outcome of ever having a COVID-19 test recorded to investigate whether observed associations were biased by differences in testing behaviour or test recording between adults living with and without children.

Vaccination of children

All children aged 12-17 years in England were first eligible for COVID-19 vaccination on 20th September 2021. To examine whether child vaccination was associated with adult COVID-19 outcomes, we conducted two additional analyses among adults aged 18-65 years.

We split the follow-up period at the timepoint when all children aged 12-17 years in a household had received two vaccine doses. In the first analysis, we censored follow-up at this timepoint, to examine the associations of adult vaccination with the study outcomes in the absence of double-vaccinated children in the household. In the second analysis, we followed individuals from this timepoint to the study end (21st February 2022), to examine associations when eligible children in a household were double-vaccinated. In this second analysis only, households where all 12-17 year olds did not complete their vaccination course were excluded. Follow-up for households with no children started on 1st October 2021 (the first full month when all 12-17 year olds were eligible for vaccines).